

Title: Why Education Matters for Global Health: Building Knowledge and Capabilities in Addressing Antimicrobial Resistance

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Abstract

Aims: The paper aims to explore how education can strengthen global and public health responses that promote health equity, capability, and sustainability. While global health challenges are acknowledged as shaped by social, economic, and cultural determinants, the Agenda 2030 highlights education in promoting equitable and sustainable health outcomes. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) provides an illustrative case to examine these topics.

Methods: The paper operationalised qualitative and interpretive meta-analysis, integrating findings from published papers on AMR. The analysed papers examined health education across sectors. Guided by frameworks on social determinants of health, capability-oriented approaches, and wicked problems in global health, an iterative interpretive thematic analysis identified recurring patterns in how education contributes to global health engagement with AMR.

Results: Three primary themes were identified regarding the role of education in shaping how AMR is understood and addressed: i) education as a basis for contextually relevant AMR knowledge, values, and responsibility, ii) from health literacy to health capability and iii) engaging AMR as a complex health governance and health sustainability challenge. Education is highlighted as having the potential to connect AMR challenges to everyday experiences and to support the navigation of contextual constraints and competing values related to AMR.

Conclusions: The paper details why education matters for global and public health by shaping understandings and promoting capabilities and practices in addressing complex health challenges. The discussion highlights the importance of integrating education within global health agendas and emphasises the interdependence of quality education and good health in promoting equitable and sustainable health outcomes.

Keywords: global health, antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial stewardship, public health, health education, health literacy, health equity, social determinants of health, sustainable development goals, qualitative research

Word count: 2989 words

Background

Faced with increasing global and public health challenges (henceforth discussed as global health), education is framed as a key pathway to promote health equity, capability, and sustainability, shaping access to sustainable health care, participation in the healthcare system and the capability of individuals and communities to navigate complex health challenges (1, 2). With links to healthcare access, health outcomes and thus health equity, education is presented in previous research, including Nordic and non-Nordic comparisons, as a common socioeconomic indicator of health (3).

In a global setting where health challenges are becoming increasingly complex and interconnected, biomedical interventions alone are seldom enough, resulting in renewed consideration being given to education as a determinant of health. As part of the 2030 Agenda, SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) is often connected to SDG 4 (Quality Education), indicating the mutually reinforcing goals of health and education. Knowledge, critical reflection and the development of values and social responsibility are all key components of ensuring equitable health outcomes, which education provides (4). Educational disparities, therefore, represent a risk to SDG 3 as they exacerbate health inequalities in terms of health behaviours, policy engagement, healthy behaviour, and health outcomes.

This framing of education as a determinant of health aligns with the perspective of health outcomes as shaped by social, economic, and cultural conditions, with health inequalities as results of these conditions and thus possible to address (5). Education promotes the capacity for individuals to act and make health-supporting decisions as part of this socio-economic landscape, enabling the extension of global health efforts beyond behaviour-change (6-9).

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) presents a pressing global and public health challenge that risks undermining the long-term sustainability of healthcare and disproportionately affects vulnerable communities with limited access to effective healthcare. In addition to clinical solutions and antimicrobial stewardship, global health efforts seeking to address AMR require the development of health capabilities of critical reflections and decision-making as well as informed policy-making, in turn relying on a broad idea of education (1, 2, 10-12). How education navigates and negotiates antimicrobials, resistant microbes, and questions of responsibility is key as exemplified in the

variability of educational approaches and the need to integrate knowledge with practical competencies in AMR curriculum development among healthcare students in Norway (13).

Considering the potential of educational interventions for the development of health capabilities, including knowledge, critical reflection, values and decision-making, highlights how long-term mitigation is likely to rely on integrating AMR approaches within educational settings. Including education as a key component of global health would thus allow for the development of communities that can responsibly and critically engage with health information and make reflective decisions on their health and that of their communities. Understanding why education matters for global health as a driver of sustainable health practices is essential in addressing current and emerging health challenges.

Aims

This paper aims to explore how education can strengthen global health responses that promote health equity, capability, and sustainability. Operationalising antimicrobial resistance as a case, we ask the following research question, how can education contribute to global health responses to AMR that promote health equity, capacity and sustainability?

Methods

This paper operationalises a qualitative and interpretive meta-analysis method to integrate findings from a body of research, conducted between 2021 and 2026, which explored AMR education conceptually and empirically as a topic of global health (14). The strength of the chosen methodological approach lies in that it allows for the integration of complex and contextual research findings as part of conceptual development, which aligns with the paper's aim and the tradition in global health to engage as a result of social processes. Education can thus be convincingly approached as a determinant of health.

The material analysed in this paper includes nine peer-reviewed publications co-authored by the researcher and published between 2023 and 2026 (see Table 1 in the Appendix). Papers were included on the basis that they all engaged with education in relation to health, food and AMR in various ways,

together contributing conceptually and empirically to understanding education in global health. Crucially, the included papers share an epistemological and theoretical basis. The decision to analyse an author-led corpus through the use of meta-analysis was justified methodologically as the studies were part of a coherent research trajectory to explore education in global health through the case of AMR across multiple social and institutional settings. The cross-paper analysis spans secondary and higher education, professional learning, global health communication, sustainability education, and policy contexts, principally in global south settings. While presenting a limitation in the breadth of studies that are included, the choice to use papers published by the author is supported by qualitative analysis methodologies aimed at deep comparative analysis of theoretically aligned research (15, 16).

In analysing the paper, an equity-oriented global health framework was utilised in which we integrated the concepts of social determinants of health (5, 17), capability-oriented approaches to health and education (1, 2), and theories of wicked problems in global health (18, 19).

We used an iterative, four-step interpretive analysis process, starting with mapping the papers, followed in the second and third steps by the identification of key concepts and comparison to outline recurring patterns in how education could contribute to global health. In the fourth step, we developed analytical themes using reflective thematic analysis with an emphasis on how education can contribute to global health efforts across contexts (20). The analysis focused on the published papers and thus did not include a re-analysis of the underlying research materials. Through this methodological approach, we aimed for analytical transferability rather than statistical generalisability, and results should be read as such. Since the material consisted of previously published papers, no additional ethical approval was required.

Results

Education as a basis for contextually relevant AMR knowledge, values, and responsibility

Throughout the papers, education was shown to be key to how AMR is conceptualised, crucially in moving beyond traditional notions of antimicrobial stewardship and single messages of needing to avoid misusing antimicrobials. Instead, the papers highlight the potential of education to shift the focus towards more contextually relevant understandings of AMR, including how human

antimicrobial practices in the clinic and outside interact with microbes to create both unique health challenges and opportunities. An important recurring insight was how educational framings influenced whether AMR became a distant and individual biomedical problem of mostly others or a shared social challenge linked to the everyday practices of food production and consumption, healthcare access, as well as water and hygiene.

By connecting AMR to research participants' lived experiences, including social and cultural contexts, education was highlighted as shaping meaning-making processes. This was exemplified in how Zimbabwean students' interpretations of the impacts of antimicrobial use and resistance for health engaged with social and structural conditions, such as access to healthcare and economic and social pressures. Across the analysed papers, education did not only provide information and awareness, but its key role was positioning AMR as a relevant topic in the lives of individuals and communities, including their social, cultural and material realities.

In addition, a recurring theme was how education had a key function to support participants in developing critical evaluative abilities and values around AMR. This encompassed questions of individual and shared responsibilities for preventing and addressing AMR, along with subsequent implications for health equity in terms of who bears the long-term cost for resistance.

Finally, the analysed papers highlighted how across curricula, classroom discourses, and reflections of participating students show how health narratives often prioritise biomedical understandings and put the responsibility on individuals and groups, such as small-scale farmers, for preventing and addressing what has been shown in research to be significantly structural challenges of AMR. Educational settings were thus framed as double-sided arenas, they provide opportunities for AMR to be linked to students' experiences and thus become relevant in their everyday lives. Simultaneously, education risked functioning as a vehicle through which responsibility for large, complex and structural global health challenges, such as AMR, is outsourced to individuals and marginalised groups. The papers thus indicated the importance of education for global health as an arena where narratives about what is "good health", who is responsible for promoting health, and what are acceptable health risks were both reproduced and contested. Crucially, where education came to more directly support the engagement with AMR as a shared social and structural challenge

beyond narratives of individual irrationality and need for behavioural change, was when questions of health equity were explicitly addressed.

From health literacy to health capability

A further recurring theme was the distinct but related notions of health literacy and health capability. Throughout the analysed papers, the development of knowledge and awareness about the health challenges related to antimicrobial use and AMR as part of education was common and persistent. Meanwhile, challenges often emerged in terms of bridging the implementation gap and putting this knowledge and awareness into practice, in which the ability to realise health literacy depended on social, economic and cultural contextual factors, as well as institutional and structural conditions, as they emerged as having a significant impact. As these factors and conditions are partly outside the control of individuals, this highlights the need for and potential in education, acknowledging and engaging with these determinants of health to support students in developing health capabilities as part of meaningful AMR-related practices.

The role of education in capability development was clearest in the enabling of students to negotiate and navigate conflicting values, such as balancing biomedical health advice with economic necessity, social and cultural expectations, or limited access to healthcare. The paper analysis thus illustrated a shift as part of educational processes from the assumption that individual behavioural change would follow from the development of individual knowledge and awareness, towards education enabling students to build their capability to achieve their health-related beings and doings in situations characterised by contextual constraints. Rather than being primarily prescriptive, education was thus indicated to have the potential as part of global health to support AMR resilience by equipping students with tools of critical reflection and to make contextually relevant decisions under conditions of uncertainty and constraints.

Engaging AMR as a complex health governance and health sustainability challenge

In the papers, ranging across upper-secondary education, higher education and professional learning educational settings, a recurring characterisation of AMR was its complexity as a “wicked” problem,

encompassing uncertainty and competing priorities and values. To account for this, there was an emphasis in the papers on education needing to move beyond the transfer of information and the prescription of certain behaviours and practices towards approaches that embraced the complexity of AMR. Such educational approaches included the use of case methodologies grounded in the lived experiences of students as well as interdisciplinary workshops, where experts from various fields of medicine, veterinary and environmental sciences, as well as dietetics, together engaged with the shared health challenge of AMR. This indicated how education can enable engagement with global health challenges such as AMR beyond linear relations of cause and effect.

Crucially, the educational processes detailed in the analysed papers were shown to be able to support systems thinking around food, health and AMR as they enabled students to relate microbial processes to individual food choices and communal reliance on food systems and food security. Education, thus, was indicated to have a key role in situating AMR as a topic of global health and health equity framed as part of broader sustainability challenges. To this end, AMR became an issue that warranted deep engagement and reflection through education to foster an understanding of global health challenges as more than individual biomedical issues but as societal challenges that require joint responses bringing together experiences and expertise across sectoral boundaries of human, animal and environmental health.

This cross-sectoral aspect with regard to AMR was further highlighted in the analysis of multiple papers, in which education began to bridge the gap between individual meaning-making and policy and governance processes. Through acknowledging AMR health governance challenges and pushing for the integration of policy perspectives, education was indicated to enable students to position their practices as part of and contributing to larger health institutional frameworks and antimicrobial stewardship efforts. Making these connections, students were able to critically reflect on how addressing AMR includes navigating policy and regulation, negotiating sometimes competing values and managing responsibility under uncertain conditions. Crucially, allowed education to contribute to new perspectives regarding accountability and the building of shared agency and engaged participation in antimicrobial stewardship, moving away from tendencies towards narrow individual compliance to prescriptive behaviours of antimicrobial use.

Discussion

Education as a key determinant in addressing complex global health challenges

The results of the qualitative and interpretive meta-analysis conducted in this paper outline how education comes to matter for global health. In addition to more traditional pathways of sharing information and raising awareness, education can take the form of a determinant of individuals and communities' capacity to understand, critically reflect, make decisions about and change practices to address global health challenges. This is especially key as many global health challenges reach beyond the biomedical space and are characterised by complexity and questions of health equity. Previous research argues that addressing such challenges requires systems thinking, interdisciplinary engagement, and reflexivity (21). Examples from previous research include the effect of education in reducing adult mortality (7) and the impact of parental education in mitigating child mortality as well as lifelong health inequalities (8).

Through the analysis of papers on AMR education as a case for the relevance on education in global health we have been able to illustrate how education can operate as a public-health intervention in mediating awareness raising and mediation of knowledge as well as the development of critical reflective abilities, values and ultimately capabilities for individual and collective practices to address global health challenges under diverse contextual conditions. Based on these insights, we argue that SDG 3, health and well-being, needs to be considered together with SDG 4, quality education, as key components for sustainable health outcomes as part of global health agendas.

Education as a structural and equity-shaping determinant of global health

Emerging from the results are insights into how education shapes approaches to and engagement with global health challenges, which, as shown in the case of AMR, are embedded in social, economic, and cultural conditions. Education shapes how global health challenges are understood, navigated, and addressed through practice (22-24). Across the analysed papers, education was shown as informing how learners understood the relationships between microbes, antimicrobials, and individual as well as shared responsibilities, whether AMR was perceived as a distant biomedical issue or as a socially produced and shared problem (25, 26).

These results align with Hahn & Truman (9), who emphasise the importance of education as a pathway for promoting health equity and global health objectives. Framing education as key for access to information and the development of knowledge and critical reflective skills indicates that limitations in access to quality education relevant to individuals and communities experience risks undermining health-related decision-making that is simultaneously effective and equitable (25, 27).

While education presents significant potential for global health, the results highlight the importance of how education is conceptualised as it can simultaneously reinforce dominant health narratives and marginalise some social groups, raising questions about “health for whom” (3, 25, 26). These insights reflect the conceptual point made by Altová et al. (6) on education's impact on participation in preventive health behaviours, such as screening for cervical cancer. Such a health equity-sensitive approach would enable education to contribute to key global health objectives (7, 8). Education in global health is thus a multilayered resource that necessitates careful consideration with regard to how it is operationalised (26, 28).

From individual responsibility to collective capability in addressing AMR

A further thematic insight emerging from the results is how education, when framed narrowly, risks putting significant responsibility on individuals who are not in a position to comply with recommended practices while obscuring the more social and structural dimensions of global health challenges (23, 25). Meanwhile, students can be supported in situating these challenges within broader contexts of health inequalities through contextually and experientially relevant educational approaches, as it allows for the exploration of questions of healthcare access and responsibilities (22). In addition, the results indicate how education contributes to global health most effectively when it looks past individual behaviour-change and considers the development of capabilities. Crucially, increased knowledge of AMR was indicated to not to be in a linear relationship with more reflective and informed decision-making nor changes in the practices of antimicrobial use and stewardship (25). To achieve these outcomes, there is a need to engage with constraining contextual conditions, including social, economic and cultural pressures as well as limitations to healthcare access (22, 25, 28). Students can, through education, strengthen their abilities to address these everyday conditions,

through education supporting their navigating associated uncertainty, value tensions and trade-offs (26, 29, 30). This speaks to previous research, which has emphasised that the primary impact of education on improving health outcomes is the development of capabilities that enable individuals and communities to navigate the structural circumstances that act as determinants of health (9).

Conclusions

This paper used a qualitative and interpretive meta-analysis to explore, through the case of AMR, how education can strengthen global and public health responses that promote health equity, capability, and sustainability. Across the nine analysed papers, our results highlighted the impact of education in shaping understandings, critical reflections and decision-making around questions of responsibility and health equity, as well as the possibility for individual and joint practices to address global and public health challenges. Through the operationalisation of AMR as a case, the analysis highlights the importance to view education as more than a support to global and public health, but rather a key component that enables the processes of awareness, understanding, critical reflection, decision-making and ultimately practices that become the basis for building a more sustainable and equitable global health development that links SDG 4 (Quality Education) with SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being).

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

Data availability

All analysed data is available as published and referenced papers

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Tables

Reference	Main contribution to the meta-analysis
<p>Oljans, E., & Mickelsson, M. (2026). Bridging The Knowledge Gap: Capacity Building and Education on Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR).</p>	<p>Provided the structural framing of education as a capacity-building mechanism beyond awareness. Anchored the interpretation of education as a governance-linked and systemic public-health intervention.</p>
<p>Oljans, E., Usai, T., Chinofunga, D. and Mickelsson, M. (2025). Exploring health for who: Discourse analysis of health-related values in upper secondary education.</p>	<p>Outlined education's dual role in either reinforcing or challenging health inequalities. Introduced the "health for whom?" lens central to the equity argument in the meta-analysis.</p>
<p>Mickelsson, M., Oljans, E. Case vignettes-based workshops as a tool to facilitate interdisciplinary engagement with complex problems in sustainability education.</p>	<p>Demonstrated how case-based, interdisciplinary approaches enhance systems thinking and collective engagement with complex problems, informing the "wicked problem" framing of AMR.</p>
<p>Mickelsson, M., Oljans, E. (2025) Agile Policies for Antimicrobial Resistance: A Contextual Approach to Sustainable Health Challenges.</p>	<p>Connected education to governance structures and policy responsiveness. Strengthened the argument that education bridges individual understanding and institutional action.</p>
<p>Oljans, E., & Mickelsson, M. (2025). Navigating complexity: teaching sustainability through wicked problems in higher education.</p>	<p>Provided the conceptualisation of AMR as a wicked problem and demonstrated the value of complexity-oriented educational models in developing reflexivity and systemic understanding.</p>
<p>Mickelsson, M., & Oljans, E. (2025). Food, health and sustainability: How students navigate conflicting choices in social contexts.</p>	<p>Showed how values, social norms, and contextual constraints shape health decision-making. Supported the shift from individual behaviour models to contextualised capability development.</p>

<p>Oljans, E., Usai, T., Chinofunga, D. and Mickelsson, M. (2024). Balancing diets: diverse values shaping sustainable food choices.</p>	<p>Illustrated how educational framing influences how students balance ethical, environmental, and health considerations. Reinforced the interpretative function of education.</p>
<p>Mickelsson, M., Usai, T., Chinofunga, D., & Oljans, E. (2023) 'Health communication for AMR behaviour change: Zimbabwean students' relationships with the microbial world'.</p>	<p>Demonstrated that AMR knowledge does not automatically translate into behaviour change. Highlighted cultural meanings and contextual constraints shaping stewardship practices.</p>
<p>Mickelsson, M., Usai, T., Chinofunga, D., & Oljans, E. (2023). From Being Literate about Health to Becoming Capable of Achieving Health: Health literacy capabilities of Zimbabwean school youth.</p>	<p>Provided the capability-based framework central to the analysis. Showed that literacy must translate into contextualised capacity to act, reinforcing the collective capability argument.</p>

Table 1. Overview of studies included in the qualitative meta-analysis